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The Perception of Employment Insecurity in Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022

It decreased on average by 17.17%

Istat calculates the value of the perception of employment insecurity in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the percentage of employed people who believe it is probable that they will lose their current job in the next 6 months and that it is little or not at all probable that they will find another similar one out of the total number of employed people. The data refers to the period 2018-2022 for the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the perception of employment insecurity in 2022. Basilicata is in first place by value of the perception of employment insecurity with a value of 8.9 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 7, 8, and from Sicily with a value of 7.5 units. In the middle of the table are Tuscany and Umbria with a value of 5 units followed by Emilia Romagna and Molise with a value of 4.8 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a value of 3.7 units, followed by Piedmont and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 3.6 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in employment insecurity between 2018 and 2022. Sicily is in first place with a value of the percentage change in employment insecurity between 2018 and 2022 equal to an amount of 0.00. Basilicata follows where the percentage change in the value of the percentage change in employment insecurity between 2018 and 2022 decreased by -4.30% going from an amount of 9.30 units to a value of 8.90 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to -5.26% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.80 units up to a value of 3.60 units equal to a variation of -0.20 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Valle d'Aosta with a variation equal to an amount of -14.81% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.40 units up to a value of 4.60 units or corresponding to an amount of -0.80 units. Abruzzo follows with a percentage change of -16.44% or from 7.30 units in 2018 up to a value of 6.10 units in 2022 corresponding to a change of -1.20 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to an amount of -17.57% corresponding to a variation from 7.40 units up to a value of 6.10 units or equal to a variation of -1.30. Piedmont closes the ranking with a variation equal to -29.41% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.10 units up to a value of 3.60 units or equal to an amount of -1.50 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to an amount of -32.31% with a reduction from 6.50 units in 2018 up to 4.40 units in 2022. Finally Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to an amount of -39.39% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.60 units up to 4.00 units. Overall between 2018 and 2022, the perception of employment insecurity decreased in the Italian regions on average, going from a value of 6.44 units to 5.33 units or equal to a variation of -1.11 units corresponding to -17.17%.

Perception of employment insecurity in Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 5.10 units to a value of 3.90 units or equal to a variation of -23.53% corresponding to a variation of -1.20 units.

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The value of the perception of employment insecurity in the North West decreased from 4.90 units in 2018 to a value of 3.70 units in 2022 or equal to a variation of -1.20 units corresponding to a variation of - 24.49%. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in the North-East decreased between 2018 and 2022 from an amount of 5.30 units to a value of 4.20 units or equal to an amount of -1.10 units corresponding to a variation of -20.75%. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in Central Italy decreased from an amount of 5.50 units to a value of 4.70 units between 2018 and 2022 corresponding to a variation of -0.80 units equal to at an amount of -14.55%. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 7.80 units in 2018 to a value of 6.80 units in 2022, i.e. corresponding to a variation of an amount of -1.00 units equal to an amount of -12.82%. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 7.70 units in 2018 to a value of 6.50 units in 2022 or corresponding to a reduction from an amount of -1.20 units equal to an amount of -15.58%. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in the Islands decreased from an amount of 7.90 units to a value of 7.60 units in 2022 corresponding to a variation of -0.30 units equal to a value of -3 ,80%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two different clusters are therefore identified:

- Cluster 1: Sicily, Sardinia, Campania, Calabria, Basilicata, Puglia, Abruzzo, Marche;
- Cluster 2: Lazio, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Veneto, Molise, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Emilia Romagna, Liguria.

The analysis shows the presence of an ordering between the clusters as indicated below: $C1 > C2$. It therefore follows that the perception of employment insecurity in the southern regions tends to be higher than the corresponding value in the northern regions. Molise is the only southern region that participates in Cluster 2, i.e. the cluster of the northern regions. On the contrary, the Marche is the only non-southern region to participate in Cluster 1 or the cluster of the southern regions.

Conclusions. In summary from the data analysis we can note the following propositions:

- The perception of employment insecurity decreased in all Italian regions between 2018 and 2022 with the sole exception of Sicily where this value remained unchanged;
- The perception of employment insecurity between 2018 and 2022 decreased in the North by an amount of -23.53%, in the South by an amount of -15.58% and in the Central Italy by a value of 14.55% ;
- The central-northern regions present a much lower value of the perception of employment insecurity than the southern regions.

However, considering that in 2022 the number of employed people was equal to 23,250,000, since the number of employed people who perceive insecurity in employment is equal to 5.33% it follows that approximately 1,239,225 employed in Italy fear for their working future. A value that should not be overlooked by economic policies. It is necessary to offer workers, even when they are flexible, even when they are precarious, training and work paths that can allow them to lengthen their expectations relating to employment by reducing the perceived insecurity regarding the stability of employment.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

